

AI SYSTEMS AND SHOPPABLE VIDEO FOR SEAMLESS CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE AND PRODUCT CUSTOMIZATION IN E-COMMERCE

Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullaevich

Independent researcher, Tashkent Financial Institute

Beknazarova Saida Safibullayevna,

Tashkent University of Information Technology named after
Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, professor, Dsc.

Abstract: *The prevalence of online videos provides an opportunity for e-commerce companies to exhibit their product ads in videos by recommendation. In this paper, we propose an advertising system named video e-Commerce to exhibit appropriate product ads to particular users at proper time stamps of videos, which takes into account video semantics, user shopping preference and viewing behavior feedback by a two-level strategy.*

Keywords: *shoppable video, e-commerce, appropriate product*

Brands have already been adding videos to their online business strategies. However, combining creative and engaging videos is not enough. To stay ahead, companies must include unique ways that deliver value to customers. This is where shoppable videos come into the picture[1].

Shoppable video is a content type that is either visible on the landing page or social media channels. It attracts customers and directs them to the product pages. With the help of a video, customers can see varieties of products while watching the video. And, if they like any of them, they can click on it. When clicked, the user is directed to another page containing information such as:

1. Reviews
2. Product details
3. Buying details
4. Contact information

The shoppable content empowers eCommerce brands to deliver direct and instant sales. A link embeds hotspots into a video to make certain parts clickable. Whenever any shoppable eCommerce video plays, customers can click on icons floating over the models. The more the customers click on the link or video, the higher the click-through rates. The aim behind shoppable videos is to meet the direct purchasing desire that a customer gets after viewing the product.

Businesses use some popular platforms like YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat for video marketing, which results in a higher reach to the target audience and an improved shopping experience[2].

The Importance of Shoppable Videos

With the rise of technology, retail brands can combine content and commerce. It creates a real experience to assist, engage, and inspire the target audience with smart shopping decisions. Retailers and marketers can use shoppable videos as a personalized customer engagement strategy that creates a better user experience and helps customers in their decision-making process.

How does Shoppable Video Work?

By integrating shoppable features in the videos, brands reduce the number of steps a customer needs to follow to make a purchase. You do not have to scroll up and down the product page or wishlist or remember the product. With clickable feature integration, you can see/touch/try the product, thanks to advanced technology – Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). By incorporating an interactive part in a video, retailers can leverage customers' inclination and interest in the product and make them buy right away

Benefits of shoppable video for eCommerce Businesses

With the ever-changing eCommerce landscape, you have to meet your customers where they are: online. [In 2020, 96% of consumers increased their online video consumption, and 9 out of 10 viewers said that they wanted to see more videos from brands and businesses.](#) With Mindstamp's interactive video platform you're able to not only meet your consumers' expectations by creating video content they want to see, but exceed them by creating engaging interactive content that set your brand apart from the competition.

Friction in the shopping experience is the amount of effort the individual must put in to make a purchase. In the past, when a viewer wanted to purchase a product promoted in a video they would have to find the description, follow a link, track down the item, add it to the cart, and finally check out. With each step, the likelihood of the viewer to purchase falls significantly. However, with shoppable videos, making a purchase can be as simple as two clicks, which increases the viewer's likelihood to purchase[3].

Benefits of shoppable video for online shoppers

From the shopper's perspective, users want immediate results from a simple process. [74% of consumers are at least somewhat likely to buy based on experiences alone](#), and \$98B/year is left on the table by companies who fail to provide "simple" experiences to their consumers. The solution is interactive shoppable videos; your eCommerce business can provide a simple process with immediate next steps by using interactive features to provide product information and the ability to purchase a product directly from within the video. 80% of customers are more likely to purchase a product or service from a brand that provides personalized experiences, and 72% of consumers in 2019 only engage with marketing messages that are customized to their specific interests. This confirms the future of eCommerce is personalizing the experience with shoppable video to maximize viewer engagement. Mindstamp's interactive video platform offers a variety of personalization capabilities, from using text-based personalization to address the viewer's name and interests throughout the video, to branching that allows the viewer to decide the direction of their viewing experience.

Shoppable videos are gaining traction, and the combination of [video](#) and [commerce](#) is probably going to change the shopping experience in the future. It will open doors for partnerships, brand engagements and improve overall business results [4].

The two words are often used interchangeably when discussing how to create tailored experiences. The goal of personalization and customization is the same: to create a unique, tailored experience for shoppers. But, there is a slight difference, **Customization is done by the shopper**

Customization examples:

- adding details to an online profile
- choosing how to view a product
- following fashion influencers within a shopping app

Personalization is done by the app or eCommerce platform.

Personalization examples:

- sending push notifications based on previous customer behavior
- showing shoppers, a specific landing page after they abandon a shopping cart
- product recommendations

Personalization and customization are closely related. With better shopper information (which a shopper would customize), personalization tools can work more effectively.

A global online survey on senior managers and executives conducted in 2016-2017 reveals that only 15 % of firms do not have any AI plans. Artificial intelligence unfolded avenues for competitive advantage, but it is not free from challenges. Moving ahead of digital transformations, AI-driven approaches such as data science and new technologies like extended reality, robots, recommender systems, the internet of things and conversational agents, etc., are the modern ways to improve customer experience. According to a Bain & Company survey, most organizations incorporate AI based customer experience tools for sustainable competitive advantage⁸. The following section of the article addresses six emerging AI-enabled technologies that can transform

the customer experience. Transformation requires a cross-functional team consisting of data scientists, process engineers, business managers, technology specialists, domain specialists', etc. The CX team is responsible for understanding customer behavior in real-time and acting accordingly to make the process more agile, strong, and personalized. Tracking the individual customer journey can bring a seamless experience to customers. Customers can be benefited from a positive experience through some compensation if they face any pain point in the journey. For example, a study on a leading fast food restaurant reveals – falling of food items from the table while eating, is taken as a severe event in the customer journey and the staff of the restaurant serves another dish to the customer, without charging any extra bill on the new dish. Here the individual journey is more important to such restaurants, and customers are delighted with a memorable experience [5].

According to a BCG survey report, only 29 percent of consumers accept that data results in better services, whereas 75 percent of consumers are concerned for their privacy and now limit themselves from sharing any personal information online. Customers trade their privacy with personalization and this conundrum is referred to as the personalization– privacy paradox. The following matrix is proposed to solve this paradox:

Benefits of Product Customization in e-Commerce

Appeal to a growing demand for product customization: One of the reasons why customization is more important than ever is the emotion attached to these products. When a customer feels like the product is truly theirs, it goes from being merely another product to a personal belonging.

Encourage customers to pay more. In addition to boosting sales and customer satisfaction, a product customizer or configurator can actually get people to spend more on a product. In fact, one report from The Motley Fool found that customized products can sell for as much as 50% more than those sold in physical stores. The reason for this is that customers are more likely to pay higher prices if the product they're buying feels more personal.

Increase customer loyalty. Personalized products can also build more customer loyalty, as shoppers feel more satisfied purchasing from companies that give them some control over their purchases. When people have a positive experience using product customizers on an online store, they'll be more likely to return to that store for future purchases.

Set more realistic delivery time expectations. Many e-Commerce platforms such as Amazon have built unrealistic expectations when it comes to delivery times. Customers want the instant gratification of next-day or even same-day delivery, but when it comes to businesses offering product customization, a Deloitte poll shows that online shoppers are willing to wait a little longer for delivery.

This is because customers understand that a customized product takes more time to process and manufacture than generic products, with the added expectation of higher quality.

Boost e-Commerce sales.

From simpler custom-printed T-shirts to more complex products that feature different colors, materials, dimensions, or even varying functionality, retailers can see a significant boost in sales by offering customization. If people know what to expect from the products they buy, they're more likely to be happy with their purchase and confidently click "order now."

Gain better data about customers. Offering product personalization through customization software can give your brand even more insight into your customers. Based on the different features that customers select in their favorite products, you can gauge customers' tastes and preferences. Using this information, you can make personalized product recommendations that are likely to appeal to them and keep them coming back.

Conclusion

Ecommerce personalization, at its core, is about creating uniquely tailored experiences for customers online. In the early days of the web, it could be as simple as suggesting products customers may like, based on viewing history. As technology advanced, ecommerce personalization methods became more advanced. With more data points to collect, retailers can use customer data such as browsing history, viewing location, age demographics, or previous purchases to create a unique online shopping experience.

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